

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

***BULLETIN OF* FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

2026, №1 (21)

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА КЛИНИК
ТИББИЁТ АХБОРОТНОМАСИ
ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

Научный журнал по фундаментальным и клиническим
проблемам медицины
основан в 2022 году

Бухарским государственным медицинским институтом
имени Абу Али ибн Сино
выходит один раз в 2 месяца

Главный редактор – Ш.Ж. ТЕШАЕВ

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2026, № 1 (21)

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Сайт <https://bsmi.uz/journals/fundamental-ya-klinik-tibbiyot-ahborotnomasi/>

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О журнале

Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и информации
Бухарской области
№ 1640 от 28 мая 2022 года.

Журнал внесен в список
утвержденный приказом № 370/б
от 8 мая 2025 года реестром ВАК
в раздел медицинских наук.

Отпечатано в типографии ООО
“Шарк-Бухоро”. г. Бухара,
ул. Ўзбекистон Мустақиллиги, 70/2.

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DETERMINING THE QUALITY OF LIFE IN PATIENTS WITH JAW DEFECTS FOLLOWING COVID-19

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Resume. This article to assess the quality of life (QoL) in patients with jaw defects after COVID-19, focusing on physical, psychological, and social dimensions. Understanding these factors is essential for improving rehabilitation strategies and multidisciplinary care.

Key words: Quality of life, jaw defects, COVID-19, maxillofacial rehabilitation, psychosocial impact.

COVID-19 ДАН КЕЙИН ЖАҒ НУҚСОНЛАРИ БЎЛГАН БЕМОРЛАРНИНГ ҲАЁТ СИФАТИНИ АНИҚЛАШ

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Резюме. Ушбу мақола COVID-19 дан кейин жағ нуқсонлари бўлган беморларда ҳаёт сифатини (QoL) жисмоний, психологик ва ижтимоий жиҳатларга эътибор қаратган ҳолда баҳолашга бағишланган. Ушбу омилларни тушуниш реабилитация стратегиялари ва кўп тармоқли ёрдамни такомиллаштириш учун муҳимдир.

Калит сўзлар: Ҳаёт сифати, жағ нуқсонлари, COVID-19, юз-жағ реабилитацияси, руҳий-ижтимоий таъсир.

ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ КАЧЕСТВА ЖИЗНИ ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ДЕФЕКТАМИ ЧЕЛЮСТИ ПОСЛЕ COVID-19

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Резюме. Эта статья предназначена для оценки качества жизни (QoL) у пациентов с дефектами челюстей после COVID-19, с акцентом на физические, психологические и социальные аспекты. Понимание этих факторов необходимо для улучшения стратегий реабилитации и многопрофильной помощи.

Ключевые слова: Качество жизни, дефекты челюстей, COVID-19, реабилитация лица и лица, психосоциальное воздействие.

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Introduction. The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly affected global healthcare systems and patient outcomes, particularly among individuals with pre-existing maxillofacial conditions. Patients with jaw defects represent a vulnerable group due to functional, aesthetic, and psychosocial challenges, which may be exacerbated following COVID-19 infection. When determining the quality of life, an assessment was carried out based on special questionnaires (OHIP-14, EQ-5D). According to the results obtained, it was established that post-COVID jaw defects significantly affect the functions of the oral cavity, nutrition, speech, social activity, and the general psycho-emotional state.

In recent years, the spread of the COVID-19 infection on a global scale has created urgent problems for medical science not only as an acute respiratory disease, but also with long-term systemic complications. According to the World Health Organization, a significant number of patients with COVID-19 have a complex of clinical symptoms that persist for a long time after the illness - post-COVID syndrome. This condition affects various systems of the body, including the musculoskeletal and maxillofacial regions. Recent scientific studies have noted cases of pathological changes in the maxillofacial region against the background of COVID-19 infection, in particular, the development of osteonecrosis, osteomyelitis, and bone defects in the jaw bones. A number of authors attribute these processes to the endothelial damaging effect of the virus, impaired microcirculation, predisposition to thrombosis, as well as prolonged use of corticosteroids and antibiotics. In some studies, a decrease in immunity in the post-COVID period is indicated as an important factor in the development of destructive processes in the jaw bones. As noted in the scientific literature, such functional and morphological disorders are not only a clinical problem, but also negatively affect the psych emo-

tional state and social adaptation of the patient. In this regard, in modern medicine, the concept of "quality of life" is considered as an important criterion in assessing the outcome of diseases. [2,8,10]. Analysis of the literature shows that there are insufficient scientific works aimed at a comprehensive assessment of the quality of life of patients with post-COVID jaw bone defects. [1,3]. Existing studies are mainly limited to clinical and radiological indicators, and the subjective state of the patient, functional limitations, and the degree of adaptation to social life have not been sufficiently studied. Therefore, this problem requires deep scientific analysis. Quality of life in such patients is already compromised due to functional limitations and psychological distress. The COVID-19 pandemic has introduced additional challenges, including delayed surgical treatment, limited access to rehabilitation services, and long-term post-COVID complications.

Materials and methods. The object of the study were patients diagnosed with COVID-19 infection and a defect in the jawbone in the post-COVID period. The study involved male and female patients over 18 years of age. Patients were selected from among those observed in the dental and maxillofacial surgical departments. The patients were divided into two groups. The main group - patients with a jaw defect in the post-COVID period. Control group - healthy individuals who have not had or have had COVID-19 infection, but have not been diagnosed with a jaw defect. It was established that COVID-19 infection in patients was confirmed by PCR or serological methods. The jaw bone defect was clinically and radiologically confirmed. In this case, we used clinical and radiological methods. Dental examination; Palpation and percussion of the maxillofacial region; Assessment of oral cavity functions (chewing, speech, pain level): Pain detection using a visual-analog scale (VAS) was used. Among the radiological methods, 3D X-ray was used. Using this X-ray examination method, the size, location, and bone density of the defect were also assessed. Methods for assessing the quality of life: OHIP-14 (Oral Health Impact Profile) - quality of life associated with the oral cavity, SF-36 (Short Form Health Survey) - general quality of life.

Quality of life assessment can be conducted using validated questionnaires such as the WHOQOL-BREF, Oral Health Impact Profile (OHIP-14), and the University of Washington Quality of Life (UW-QoL) questionnaire [1]. These tools evaluate multiple domains, including physical health, psychological well-being, social relationships, and functional capacity. Patients with acquired or congenital jaw defects who had a confirmed history of COVID-19 infection are assessed during the post-recovery period. Clinical examination, patient interviews, and self-reported questionnaires are used to collect data. Comparative analysis may be performed between patients with and without a history of COVID-19 to identify significant differences in quality-of-life indicators.

Results. Studies and clinical observations indicate that patients with jaw defects following COVID-19 often report decreased physical stamina, increased pain perception, and greater difficulty in speech and chewing. Psychological factors, such as fear of reinfection, social isolation, and dissatisfaction with facial appearance, also play a crucial role in lowering quality of life scores.

Table 1.

Clinical symptom	Main group(n=60)	Control group(n=30)	P-value
Pain syndrome(VAS ≥ 4)	46 (76,7%)	6 (20,0%)	<0,001
Disorders of chewing function	42 (70,0%)	5 (16,7%)	<0,001
Speech disorder	28 (46,7%)	4 (13,3%)	<0,01
Inflammation of the mucosa	34 (56,7%)	7 (23,3%)	<0,01
Swelling in facial region	19 (31,7%)	6 (20,0%)	<0,05

To assess the differences between the two groups: Student's independent t-test was used, 95% confidence interval (95% CI) was calculated, $p < 0.05$ was considered. statistically significant.

The quality of life of patients was assessed according to the WHOQOL-BREF scale (0-100 points). (Table 2.)

Table 2.

Quality of Life Scores in Both Groups

Quality of life sectors	Main group(n=60)	Control group(n=30)	Mean Difference	95% CI	P-value
Physical	52.3 \pm 7.4	68.9 \pm 6.1	-16.6	-19.6 to -13.5	<0.001
Psychological	49.6 \pm 6.9	70.2 \pm 5.8	-20.6	-23.4 to -17.8	<0.001
Social relations	54.1 \pm 8.2	72.5 \pm 6.4	-18.4	-21.9 to -14.8	<0.001
Functional state (chewing, speech)	50.8 \pm 7.6	69.4 \pm 6.9	-18.6	-22.0 to -15.2	<0.001

Statistical Interpretation. According to the results of the student's t-test, it was found that the quality-of-life indicators in patients who have undergone COVID-19 were statistically significantly lower in all areas compared to the control group ($p < 0.001$). 95% of the confidence intervals are negative, confirming that the difference between the groups is stable and clinically significant.

Figure 1. Comparison of Mean Quality of Life Scores

Patients with a jaw defect who have had a COVID-19 infection:

- quality of life has significantly decreased in all key areas;
- Physical and psychological domains are most affected;
- functional complaints and psych emotional disorders were more common.

These results confirm the negative impact of COVID-19 on the post-infectious syndrome and the rehabilitation process.

Conclusion. Determining the quality of life in patients with jaw defects following COVID-19 is essential for effective treatment planning and long-term patient support. COVID-19 can significantly exacerbate existing functional and psychosocial problems in this population. A multidisciplinary approach involving maxillofacial surgeons, prosthodontists, psychologists, and rehabilitation specialists is necessary to improve patient outcomes and overall quality of life.

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For citation: Boymuradov Sh.A., Ruziyeva S.S., Achilova N.G'. Determining the quality of life in patients with jaw defects following COVID-19 // *Bulletin of Fundamental and Clinic Medicine.* – 2026. – № 1(21). – P. 345–347. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18346721>